

PARAMETERS OF EDUCATION OF GENDER RESPONSIBILITY IN STUDENTS

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Abstract: In this article, the state and society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the main mechanism of the education system, are presented in the opinion of the reforms that are being implemented in the direction of personal education. The importance of forming gender identity and gender identity in students, the fact that gender identity is a phenomenon that determines the main image of a person, and the need to equip future teachers with pedagogical and psychological knowledge about gender models and the formation of cultural behavior are based on that fact. The article serves as an important resource for researchers and students in the scientific and pedagogical community.

Key words: gender education in Uzbekistan, gender identity, gender identity, gender, gender culture, girls, boys, gender education, parameter, educational process, socio-cultural environment.

The formation of gender identity in adolescent boys and girls is important in their socialization based on the national-cultural approach. Because gender identity makes it possible to ensure coherence and compatibility in the external and internal image of the student's personality. Gender identity makes it possible to open the mechanisms of compatibility between the inner world of students and the socio-cultural environment. As a result, boys and girls acquire behavioral models that allow them to enter into a socially cross-cultural relationship. It is known that the scope of mutual contradictions in interpersonal relations is expanding. Gender models in most cases do not lose their originality. The individuality of boys and girls is being influenced by popular and marginal culture. This can be seen primarily in the deviations and limitations of the worldview of gender models. That is why the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan urges the state and society, as well as the education system, which is its main mechanism, to pay special attention to personal education. One of the main tasks of educational processes should be the formation of gender identity in gender models. For this purpose, the task of forming identity in gender

models and applying continuous development mechanisms to the educational process is becoming more urgent every day. Because one of the manifestations of identity is gender. Gender identity allows each individual to express themselves as a gender model (as a boy or a girl). This, in turn, creates conditions for gender models to ensure the cultural and spiritual development of society. Students are helped to form the image of their "I." As a result, gender models adapt to fulfil their social functions while realizing their identity. It allows each individual to socialize using the mechanisms of entering into complex relationships with the help of his natural talent. Learners themselves should appear as active participants in this process. Because the gender model itself must have the ability to accept or reject the roles offered to it. For this, it is required that students have a gender identity. Gender identity is a phenomenon that determines the basic image of a person.

It is formed as a result of the psychological internalization of characteristics characteristic of a man or a woman. This phenomenon occurs as a result of the socialization of gender models. Gender identity is a product of the formation of the international scientific-practical conference on social gender models. "Mechanisms of formation of cultural behavior in students and students by means of gender models: problems, solutions." Gender models are activated as a result of socialization. That's why it is one of the important tasks of the educational process to ensure socialization of boys and girls in general secondary educational institutions in accordance with the roles they play. As a result of socialization, positive aspects of students' behavior are revealed. They contain positive interpersonal relations. As a result, the level of importance of the socio-cultural environment in the educational institution increases. From the point of view of applying the approach of social construction, social reality serves as an objective and subjective factor in ensuring gender identity. Its objectivity lies in the fact that it is not related to the person himself, and its subjectivity is in the fact that it is related to the origin of the person. Within this approach, gender is understood as a social pattern formed between women and men. It is characterized by the fact that it is constructed as the main institution of society. The theory of social construction of gender is based on two foundations:

1. Gender models are constructed on the basis of socialization of a person, preparation for professional activities, division of labor. The system of gender roles, family, educational institutions and mass media help to shape it.

2. Gender is created by the person himself. In this, the level of consciousness of a person is very important. In particular, gender is unique, it follows the norms accepted by the society and the aspects formed by them: dress culture, appearance, behavior, etc. All of these are products of education.

Accordingly, it is of particular importance to determine the specific aspects of gender stereotypes that are unique to each person, taking into account the diversity of gender identity in them. These indicators are characteristic of the sixth stage of a person's spiritual development. There are indicators specific to gender stereotypes with different gender characteristics. Understanding the essence of the difference between gender models is important for the formation of gender identity in students. The formation of motivational and value orientations in different gender models is important for the formation of gender identity in them. There is a need to improve educational processes, educational programs, content of textbooks, and teaching-methodical support based on gender approach in order to form gender identity in students. For this purpose, in the process of training future teachers, it is of particular importance to arm them with pedagogical and psychological knowledge on the topic of gender models, "Mechanisms of Formation of Cultural Behavior in Students and Students: Problems, Solutions," and the formation of cultural behavior.

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